

PREDICTION OF TENSILE STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES CONSIDERING THE INTERFACIAL SHEAR STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

The tensile strength of unidirectional fiber composites is expected to increase according to improved interfacial shear strength due to increased load transfer capability of the matrix. Experiments, however, have demonstrated that optimum interfacial shear strength exists for maximum tensile strength, i.e., beyond the optimum point, the tensile strength of fiber composites decreases. This can be explained by the multiple fracture, i.e., when a fiber is broken, it accompanies concurrent breakage of surrounding fibers due to increased load transfer capability. Even though this ‘multiple fracture’ phenomenon is important to determine the tensile strength of fiber composites, few theoretical researches have been carried out. In this study, the tensile strength of unidirectional carbon fiber composites is predicted considering the interfacial shear strength. First, the effect of interfacial shear strength on the load transfer to surrounding fibers (i.e., local stress concentration) when a fiber is broken is analysed using finite element method, determining the stress concentration factor of each surrounding fiber. Based on the stress concentration factor, the number of the simultaneously broken fibers (i.e., the number of ‘multiple fracture’) is predicted using stochastic fiber strength distribution. Using the multiple fracture number, the tensile strength of unidirectional fiber composites is predicted, the validity of which is investigated using carbon fiber/nylon 6 composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composites (FRC) are used in various engineering field. The load in FRCs is mainly carried by the fibers. Even when a fiber is broken in composite, the load can be transferred through fiber/matrix interface, i.e., the composite is still able to carry the stress by load transfer through matrix [1]. Thus in the design of fiber-reinforced composite, the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) should be considered to predict the strength of composite. To improve the interface between fibers and resin, surface treatments such as chemical oxidation or sizing agent treatment have been applied.

The tensile strength of unidirectional (UD) fiber composites is thought to increase according to improved IFSS. When the IFSS increases, the load transfer capacity through interface and the recovery of axial stress increase. If IFSS is too high, however, the load transfer through interface affects more adjacent fibers. In previous research, the effect of IFSS on the interfacial failure mode was studied, suggesting an optimum IFSS for maximum tensile strength of UD composite [2,3]. They explained such an optimum IFSS for maximum tensile strength using micro-damage modes after breakage of fibers, i.e., too high IFSS caused the matrix crack to be propagated in sharp disk-shaped, bringing about multiple fracture and making the composites brittle. The multiple fracture phenomenon means that the fibers in composite are broken in a bundle. When a fiber is broken in composite, the load is transferred to the adjacent fibers as well as the axial fiber direction. The sudden stress concentration induced by local load-sharing on surrounding fibers brings about sudden and simultaneous fracture. Few theoretical researches about multiple fracture and composite strength have been carried out. Zweben and Rosen [4] especially studied the statistical theory of composite strength. They introduced the concept of stress concentration based on fiber failure model using Weibull distribution. In their statistical theory, the formation of multiple fractures was calculated as a probability in certain tensile

stress state and the effect of structural parameters including volume fraction and IFSS on the stress concentration was included to determine the stress concentration factor (SCF). Even though the statistical theory was implemented for multiple fiber breakage cases to only 4 breakages, the theory was used to predict the tensile strength of fiber composites.

In this study, the tensile strength of unidirectional carbon fiber composites is predicted considering the interfacial shear strength. First, the effect of IFSS on the load transfer to surrounding fibers (i.e., local stress concentration) is researched when a broken fiber exists in composite unit cell, determining the stress concentration factor of each surrounding fiber layer. Based on the stress concentration factor, the number of the simultaneously broken fibers (i.e., the number of ‘multiple fracture’) is predicted using a stochastic fiber strength distribution. Using the multiple fracture number, the tensile strength of unidirectional fiber composites is predicted, the validity of which is investigated using carbon fiber/epoxy composites.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Composite strength considering interfacial shear strength

When a fiber in bare fiber bundle is broken in tension, the broken fiber doesn’t carry load after that. In the composite, however, tensile load can be carried via the interfacial shear stress. In the regions far from the broken point, the broken fiber also carry tensile load. The length of the fiber in the composite strand where the fiber does not carry tensile load effectively around the fracture point is called an ineffective length (l_i). Then, the fibers which have fracture points at distances less than $l_i/2$ from an arbitrary cross-section of the composite strand do not carry tensile load in this cross-section. On the other hand, the fibers which do not have any fracture point in this length interval carry tensile load in this cross-section. Therefore, the fraction of the fibers which carry tensile load in an arbitrary cross section of the composite strand is given by the probability that a fiber has not been broken in the length interval. In this research the ineffective length is defined as 90 % of recovery of axial stress [1] as follows.

$$l_i = \text{Max} \left[2\lambda \ln 10, \frac{9}{10} l_c \right] \quad (1)$$

The probability that a fiber doesn’t break in ineffective length interval l_i at a certain stress is presented by Weibull parameter, i.e., $1-F(\sigma_f)$, where F is Weibull distribution function of fiber fracture. Then the probability that k fibers are not broken is presented below (equation (2)). It is assumed that if only one fiber in k fibers is broken, the whole fibers are all broken due to the stress concentration.

$$P = \left[1 - F(\sigma_f) \right]^k = \exp \left(- \frac{kl_i}{L_0} \left[\frac{\sigma_f}{\gamma} \right]^\beta \right) \quad (2)$$

The composite stress (σ_s) is given by the product of the probability of survival of fiber bundle (P) and fiber stress (σ_f). As the fiber stress increases, the composite stress also increases, however if there is a maximum value of the composite strength, the derivative should be zero ($d\sigma_s/d\sigma_f = 0$), resulting in the following equation.

$$\sigma_c = \min \left[\left(\frac{L_0}{2(\ln 10)e\beta\lambda k} \right)^{1/\beta}, \left(\frac{9L_0\tau_b}{10e(\beta+1)R_f k} \right)^{\beta+1} \gamma^{\frac{\beta}{\beta+1}} \right] \quad (3)$$

2.2 Multiple fracture model

The composite strength is determined considering the interface shear strength and another parameters including Weibull parameters or volume fraction can be obtained via additional measurements. The multiple fracture should be obtained to predict the tensile strength using equation

(3). The prediction of multiple fracture is carried out using a statistical model based on the study of Zweben and Rosen [4]. In this research, the hexagonal fiber packing is assumed. Stress concentration factor (k) concept is introduced. The stress concentration factor varies by layers (for example $k_1, k_2, k_3 \dots$). The stress concentration factor is obtained by finite element analysis between intact model and cracked model. The probability that a given element will fracture because of the increase in stress is given by equation (4), given that it has not broken under a stress. Using the concept of probability of fracture of adjacent fibers, the probability of fibers in adjacent layers can be calculated (see Figure 1). This is denoted by e_n , e.g., $e_2 = F(k_2\sigma_f) - F(\sigma_f)$.

Figure 1. Schematic presentation of the cross-section of unidirectional fiber composite with hexagonal array. The black circle at center represents first broken fiber, while next gray circles do the affected fibers.

$$\frac{F(k\sigma_f) - F(\sigma_f)}{1 - F(\sigma_f)} \cong F(k\sigma_f) - F(\sigma_f) \quad (4)$$

The probability that 2 multiple fracture is induced from 1 fracture is calculated using equation (5) below. In equation (5), the term $(1-e_1)^5$ means that 5 fibers are intact whereas only 1 fiber is broken, and the number 6 means the 6 symmetric numbers. The probability of further multiple fracture also can be calculated in the same manner as used in equation (4). The expected value of multiple fiber is calculated as the accumulation of equation (5), i.e., when the accumulative probability exceeds 1, it is determined that multiple fracture exists in the composite at the certain stress level. In Figure 2, the example of 3rd multiple fiber fracture from 2 multiple fracture cluster are presented. In this research this statistical model was implemented by MATLAB code.

$$p_2 = p_1 \times 6e_1 (1 - e_1)^5 \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Schematic diagram showing the evolution of 3rd multiple fiber fracture added to a cluster of two broken fibers.

2.3 Determination of composite strength

Figure 3 shows an example of determination of composite strength. The parameters for the calculation of composite strength and statistical model were obtained from [4]. The fiber stress can be calculated with arbitrary multiple fracture coefficient (black line). The demanded stress level to induce certain multiple fractures can be calculated (white line). The multiple fracture coefficient can be determined as the cross-point. In the example of multiple fracture coefficient of 20, the stress level required for the multiple fracture (about 5000 MPa) is higher than the calculated composite level (about 4300 MPa) (see Figure 3), thus such a multiple fracture state, i.e., multiple fracture coefficient of 20, cannot occur. A stress level where the white line is upper than the black line is not possible, finally determining the cross-point as the composite strength.

Figure 3. Determination of composite strength.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

In this study carbon fiber reinforced UD composites were prepared to validate the predictable model of the composite tensile strength. To obtain all parameters for statistical model, single fiber properties were measured and UD carbon fiber composite was tested. UD carbon fiber (Toray, T-700 grade) was spread to a tape prior to the fabrication of composites. The basic properties of carbon fiber were tested for the parametric studies of statistical models in following section. Single fiber tensile test was carried out in universal tensile machine and fiber strength was measured. The gage length was set

to be 10, 20, and 30 mm for Weibull parameters. The interfacial shear strength was measured by micro-droplet test. Blade collars were prepared making narrow slit, and the carbon fibers with micro-sized Nylon 6 resin drops (drop size of 30~60 micron) were set in the aforementioned slit. As the fiber was moved between the slit, the collar pressed the micro-drop of resin, providing the shear stress between the fiber-matrix interfaces and finally inducing interfacial failure. The stress was normalized with the fiber radius and the drop size.

Carbon fiber reinforced composite was fabricated with hand lay-up by laminating unidirectional fabrics. Fiber volume fraction is controlled to three different conditions, 48 (No 1), 52 (No 2) and 45 (No 3) % . Nylon 6 was supplied as a pellet and made to film using a hot press. The carbon fiber tape and Nylon 6 film were laminated layer by layer and pressed in a mold. The thickness was controlled to 4 mm and grinded to the final specimen size (the width of 12 mm and length of 200 mm). The carbon fiber composites were tested in tensile and bending mode. For the tensile test, the specimen was additionally grinded to have the width of 5 mm and length of 10 mm because the specimen was too strong to be broken in our tensile testing machine. A tensile testing machine (Instron 8801) was used. The tensile test was carried out at 0.06 mm/min (1 % strain per minute), while the bending test was carried out in a span length of 120 mm at cross-head speed of 2 mm/min.

Figure 4: Tensile specimen (left) and an example of the bending test (right)

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows the experimental and predictive composite strength of carbon fiber/Nylon 6 composites. Experimentally determined tensile and flexural strength shows the general trend, i.e., the strength is proportional to the fiber volume fraction. Reasonable agreement between experimental and predicted values is observed, even though higher strength was predicted. This may be due to mixed mode fracture, i.e., in simulation, after first fiber fracture, the ideal fracture without bridging of fiber fracture and delamination and fiber pull-out was assumed, whereas in the real experiment the mixed-mode can be involved. The flexural strength of carbon fiber composite is lower than that of tensile strength case, which was probably due to the delamination. When the delamination was considered, the stress concentration factor appeared to increase, bringing about decreased strength.

Figure 5: Comparison of experimental and predicted composite strength of carbon fiber/Nylon 6 composite: tensile strength (left) and flexural strength (right)

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this research the tensile strength of unidirectional fiber composites was predicted considering its interfacial shear strength. The composite strength was calculated from the view of interfacial shear strength and multiple fracture coefficients. For the calculation of multiple fracture coefficient, a statistical model was developed through MATLAB programming. The predicted tensile strength showed a reasonable agreement with experimental one, however higher composite strength determined by bending test was predicted, requiring a further study for more accurate prediction.

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